

Agent-based modelling of regional innovation systems: A literature review

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Abstract: Since the early 1990s, our understanding of how innovations develop has changed a lot. We observe a clear shift in the modeling of innovation systems in the literature. Traditionally, knowledge inputs were somehow directly linked to outputs. However, this linear (and location-based) view soon proved to be insufficient as it neglected the importance of the underlying microstructure of regions and the complexity of regional knowledge creation processes. Modeling regional innovation systems is a very challenging task, as various influencing factors have to be taken into account. In this respect, empirically based agent-based models have proven to be a promising approach. With advances in computing power and the availability of individualized data, agent-based models can model real-world scenarios and provide deeper insights into regional innovation systems. This article provides a historical background to the systems perspective of regional innovation and a comprehensive summary of the latest work on agent-based modeling as applied innovation systems, with a specific focus to the regional level. The aim is to explore the various methodologies, frameworks, and case studies and enhance our understanding of regional innovation dynamics and agent-based modeling. Despite their potential, much of the work is still purely theoretical, lacking an empirical basis and therefore unable to address real-world problems. The main challenges for current and future research are therefore the development of a consistent validation strategy that allows the replication of the models. We also argue that there are still only a limited number of studies that analyze regional innovation systems and include elements of participatory foresight in their agent-based models, although it has the potential to advance the scientific debate in the field of innovation geography.

Keywords: Regional innovation systems; Agent-based models; Systems perspective; Literature review

1. Introduction

Increasing globalization leads to regional differences becoming even more pronounced. The majority of the countries worldwide reached a political agreement in 2015 to reduce inequality among as well as within countries (UN General Assembly 2015). It is widely recognized that high levels of inequality not only hinder economic growth but also cause a whole range of other social and political problems. Furthermore, innovation is acknowledged as an essential capability for the economic and technological growth of firms, regions or countries (Romer 1990). Policy makers and academic researchers are therefore very interested in how innovations arise, and which policy measures help to reduce inequality within and between regions (Grossman and Helpman 1990; Freeman 2008; Cooke et al. 2011, among others). Our understanding of how these innovations develop has changed a lot since the early 1990s. Motivated by the success of technopoles like Silicon Valley, the prevailing view used to be that innovations are mainly driven by the physical location of research institutes and high-tech companies. Policy focused on the systemic promotion of local learning processes in order to create the competitive advantage of regions (Lee and Su 2010). Although these initiatives were occasionally successful, they have frequently failed to meet expectations, exposing the shortcomings of a technology-driven, linear perspective on innovation (Cooke 2001).¹ This has

¹ Examples include France (Sophia Antipolis) and Japan (Tsukuba, Kansai and Senda), where we can observe a certain lack of synergies between co-located laboratories and companies.

also emphasized the shortcomings of conventional models in capturing these complex dynamics and improved our understanding of how regional environments foster innovation. Traditionally, knowledge inputs were somehow directly linked to outputs, based on the idea that R&D funding in industry and universities would directly lead to patents, innovations or publications. However, this linear and location-centric view soon proved inadequate as it neglected the importance of the underlying microstructure of the regions and the complexity of regional knowledge creation processes (heterogeneity of the actors, non-linearity of the interactions between the actors and complexity of the environment). Cooke (2001) underlines the importance of a holistic view of innovation processes in regional contexts and emphasizes the interconnectedness of different actors, institutions and resources involved in promoting innovation. Innovation is not only the result of individual actions or strategies at the firm level, but is shaped by the broader regional environment, including factors such as social networks, knowledge spillovers, institutional frameworks and cooperation networks. This change in perspective contributed to the idea of Regional Innovation Systems (RIS), which highlights the value of information sharing, collaboration, and the dynamic interaction of a wide range of regional actors, such as firms, academic institutions, and governmental agencies. Against this background, agent-based modelling (ABM; the abbreviation ABM is used for "agent-based models" and "agent-based modeling" continual) have recently gained increasing interest as promising approach to better understand the underlying dynamics and mechanics that drive knowledge production and innovation in such complex systems (see, e.g., Gilbert, Pyka, and Ahrweiler (2014)), complementing the aggregate input-output perspective of traditional econometric models.

The objective of this study is to comprehensively analyze the existing body of work on ABM as applied innovation systems, with a specific attention to the regional level. We aim to explore the various methodologies, frameworks, and case studies, enabling the reader to get a systematic overview on the contributions and limitations of ABM in understanding and simulating the complex dynamics of innovation at the regional level. Understanding the possibilities but also challenges and pitfalls when exploring these systems through ABM provides valuable insights for researchers aiming to set up such models to address upcoming research debates, e.g. on the transformation of regional innovation systems in the context of the green and digital (twin) transition. Moreover, the findings from this review will contribute to a deeper understanding of the potentials and challenges of using ABM in policy-making and strategic planning for regional innovation.

We identify eleven papers that are empirical, analyze RIS, and use ABM (see Table 1 for a comprehensive overview). These studies differ not only in their parameterization, calibration, and validation strategies (e.g., some use empirical parameterization, while others are more theoretical), but also in the types of agents they include (such as firms, households, government entities, and research institutions), the methods they employ, and the research questions they address. Many papers do not meet all three criteria—being empirical, analyzing RIS, and utilizing ABM. Some use ABM but focus solely on firm-level innovation (Coccia and Watts 2020; Shi et al. 2020; Ramkumar et al. 2022, among others), while others incorporate both ABM and RIS but remain largely theoretical (Crooks, Castle, and Batty 2008; Ausloos, Dawid, and Merlone 2015, among others), offering limited empirical validation. Finally, incorporating foresight elements, such as stakeholder involvement, can enrich ABM and better align them with the needs and realities of RIS. Participatory foresight emerges as a critical tool for enhancing the applicability and acceptance of ABM-based insights in policymaking. However, the literature shows that participatory approaches remain underutilized within the context of RIS and empirical ABM.

The remainder of this study is organized as follows. We start with a brief re-capitulation of the basic systematic view of regional innovation (Section 2) and traditional econometric approaches focusing on relating inputs to outputs of regional innovation systems (Section 3).

Then Section 4 shifts attention to the core of this study, reviewing comprehensively the literature on Agent-based modelling of regional innovation systems. We distinguish between scope and methods, as well as results in the discussion of the different works. Section 0 discusses the notion of participatory modelling as an additional element that has come into play recently in the context of ABM for innovation systems in combining models with foresight methods. This refers to the consideration of experts and stakeholders in the specification and interpretation of such models for future development scenarios. The study closes with a short summary, some concluding remarks and future research perspectives (Section 6).

2. A systems perspective to regional innovation

Since the early 1990s, we have significantly changed our understanding of how innovations develop. Motivated by the success of Silicon Valley, the prevailing view used to be that innovation are mainly driven by the physical location of research institutes and high-tech companies (Cooke 2001). Policy focused on the systemic promotion of local learning processes in order to create the competitive advantage of regions (Lee and Su 2010). In some cases, this has led to the designation of entire cities as science cities or technopoles. Based on this thinking, innovations or the relationship between scientific progress and the commercialization of products and processes were modeled with linear models. The aforementioned initiatives, while sometimes useful, often fell short of expectations, highlighting the limitations of a linear, technology-driven view of innovation (Cooke 2001).²

The prevailing model neglected the importance of market demand, interactions between companies and institutions and local ecosystems in shaping innovation processes. Cooke (2001) underlines the importance of a holistic view of innovation processes in regional contexts and emphasizes the interconnectedness of different actors, institutions and resources involved in promoting innovation. Innovation is not only the result of individual actions or strategies at the firm level, but is shaped by the broader regional environment, including factors such as social networks, knowledge spillovers, institutional frameworks, and cooperation networks. This requires a shift of the policy focus from a few selected types of actors to consider the complex and dynamic interactions between different elements of the innovation ecosystem for instance universities, research organizations, firms and the institutional framework when designing strategies to promote regional development and innovation. Success depends on how effectively a RIS enhances knowledge flow, learning and interactive innovation (Cooke 2001), organizational competencies and the quality of human capital (respectively on the actors' ability and willingness to use globally distributed knowledge sources) which in turn is influenced by the regional and national knowledge infrastructure such as universities or the education system (Asheim, Grillitsch, and Trippel 2016). Cooke (2005) redefined RIS as “interacting knowledge generation and exploitation subsystems linked to global, national and other regional systems”. This provided a theoretical foundation that highlights the key elements that are particularly well captured by ABM.

3. Classical econometric approaches

In the empirical literature, various econometric methods are employed to analyze such RIS, but usually at an aggregate level of regions. In essence, the predominant approach involves multivariate statistical or econometric modeling using panel data, with patent data frequently serving as a proxy to measure knowledge outputs as the main basis for innovation. Although patent data does not perfectly capture innovation (Griliches 1979), there is still a close

² Examples include France (Sophia Antipolis) and Japan (Tsukuba, Kansai and Senda), where we can observe a certain lack of synergies between co-located laboratories and companies.

relationship between patents and inventions (Acs, Anselin, and Varga 2002). In what follows, we discuss some main works mobilizing such classic econometric approaches for exploring RIS.

To model the factors of regional knowledge production and innovation many use a knowledge production function (KPF) framework (Acs, Anselin, and Varga 2002; Greunz 2003; Gonçalves and Almeida 2009; Barra and Ruggiero 2022). These studies usually attempt to establish a direct link between a regional knowledge input (e.g. R&D in industry and at universities) and a knowledge output (e.g. patents, innovations or publications). Most of the reviewed papers apply some form of regression like Ordinary least squares regression (Fritsch and Slavtchev 2010), Maximum Likelihood Estimation Techniques (Acs, Anselin, and Varga 2002), robust negative-binomial regression model (Fritsch and Slavtchev 2010), simultaneous quantile regression (Fritsch and Slavtchev 2010), difference-in-differences analysis (Wong et al. 2022) or cross-sectional regression analysis (Furman, Porter, and Stern 2002) to analyze RIS. Others utilize Stochastic Frontier Analysis (Barra and Ruggiero 2022) or Two-Stage Least Squares Estimation (Gonçalves and Almeida 2009). The former is used to evaluate the efficiency with which the RIS converts inputs into outputs and to assess how far the RIS is compared to best practice and the latter to control for the endogenous spatial lag of the dependent variable. There is also a strand in the literature that establishes appropriate measurement indices and uses modified gravity models to study the effects of the intensity of association and the spatial pattern of technological innovation across cities on regional economic development (Montobbio and Sterzi 2013). Less common in the literature are studies using probit (Liu and Chen 2012; Amponsah Odei, Lasisi, and Kolawole Eluwole 2024) or logit models (Lee 2008) to model binary outcomes.

As Griliches (1990) points out, “not all inventions are patentable, not all inventions are patented, and the inventions that are patented differ greatly in ‘quality’, in the magnitude of inventive output associated with them”, some papers use other proxies for measuring innovation like the Community Innovation Survey (CIS) and the European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS). Evangelista et al. (2002) apply a factor analysis while using the CIS to examine the diversity of regional innovation patterns in Italy and evaluate the existence and functionality of RIS at the subnational level. Zabala-Iturriagoitia et al. (2007) utilize an input-output model in order to evaluate the performance of RIS on the basis of information from the EIS for 2002 and 2003.

Finally, there is also work on RIS and social network analysis which focus on the actors and interaction of knowledge exchange (Kauffeld-Monz and Fritsch 2013).

4. A move towards simulation

While the utility of the approaches above is exemplified within the academic literature, one of the central criticisms leveled at them is the treatment of all geographical components as largely homogeneous entities and therefore ignore the underlying microstructure of the regions. To better capture the real world and take into account the complexity of regional knowledge creation processes (heterogeneity of actors, the non-linearity of interactions between actors and the complexity of the environment), more comprehensive models are needed.

Throughout the 20th century, geography has borrowed concepts and theories from other fields, such as computer science, mathematics, and economics. The importance of simulating and grasping the effects of individual agents as well as the heterogeneity of geographical systems at various spatial and temporal scales has been reinforced by these concepts. Creating a "realistic" simulation of these processes and their effects is a major task for the geographer of the twenty-first century (Crooks and Heppenstall 2011). Increasing computing power and advances in individual-level data makes it possible to simulate real-world scenarios with the

help of computer simulation techniques. This was the beginning of ABM.³ In general, ABM are designed to reveal emergent properties from a bottom-up perspective, aiming to replicate real-world concepts, actions, relations, or mechanisms. They are utilized to anticipate future developments and outcomes (van Dam, Nikolic, and Lukszo 2013). ABM proves particularly suitable for examining the complex and adaptive nature of RIS, offering a framework to model and simulate the behavior of diverse agents and explore the dynamics of systemwide interactions between them. Ahrweiler, Pyka, and Gilbert (2004) were among the first to formally model the knowledge creation process within an ABM (SKIN model; "Self-Organizing Innovation Networks") (followed by Korber (2012) and Dünser and Korber (2017), among others).

4.1. Scope and methods

ABM has received increasing attention in a variety of disciplines over the past decade. Recently, there have also been some empirical models for regional knowledge creation that aim to analyze real scenarios (Beckenbach, Briegel, and Daskalakis 2007; Wang et al. 2014; Paier et al. 2017; Neuländtner 2020; Zhong and He 2021; Zhong, Chen, and He 2022, among others; Varga-Csajkás, Sebestyén, and Varga 2023; Amendola et al. 2024). Although most authors researching RIS argue that territorial agglomeration provides the best context for an innovation-based globalized economy due to the localized interactive learning processes and the "sticky" knowledge (based on social interaction), the approaches pursued, the theories used as conceptual building blocks and the design of the empirical analyses are very heterogeneous. To ensure realistic and reliable ABM, three procedures (parameterization, calibration, and validation (PCV)) are used, which can, however, vary a lot.⁴ For a comprehensive overview see Table 1. Moreover, there are some studies that do not focus on RIS but on firm-level innovation while using ABM.⁵

Cozzoni et al. (2021) present an ABM, that extends the SKIN model of Gilbert, Ahrweiler, and Pyka (2007) (which is based on Ahrweiler, Pyka, and Gilbert (2004)) with new elements to bring it closer to empirical evidence. They introduce a "double-industry" model in which agents (innovative firms), can belong to the automotive industry, the biomedical applications industry, or both. They simulate the dynamics between different actors collaborating in networks during the innovation process, taking into account the concept of responsible research and innovation (RRI).⁶ Bertani et al. (2021) enrich the macroeconomic model Eurace with the concept of intangible digital technology. They examine the effects of digitalization on the economy both at the micro and macro level. The model includes different agents in particular consumer goods producers, a capital goods producer, private households,

³ Apart from a few reservations, we see ABM more as a complement to conventional economic modeling. There are many research questions that are difficult to address with conventional methods that can be better tackled with ABM and vice versa.

⁴ For an extended explanation, see Crooks, Castle, and Batty (2008) and Neuländtner (2020).

⁵ Coccia and Watts (2020) propose the theory of technological parasitism and focus on how symbiotic relationships between "master" technologies and their parasitic technologies accelerate technological evolution. Shi et al. (2020) examine the impact of an information platform on accelerating the dissemination of energy-efficient technologies (EET) among SMEs. Mueller and Ramkumar (2023) analyze negative relationships within a network and innovation diffusion. Caprioli, Bottero, and Angelis (2020) use a hybrid ABM and a geographic information system to investigate the temporal diffusion and the willingness of inhabitants to adopt photovoltaic (PV) systems. Summad et al. (2023) simulate innovation diffusion in a construction project in Oman, focusing on how social interactions influence the decision-making process of agents. Ramkumar et al. (2022) use an ABM to understand which mechanisms could promote and accelerate the adoption and diffusion of eco-innovations. Müller, Kudic, and Vermeulen (2021) examines how the structure of technological knowledge impacts the collaborative knowledge discovery process. They do so by employing a complex adaptive systems perspective and develop an ABM in which firms seek to discover new knowledge by combining previously discovered knowledge.

⁶ By considering RRI, the Horizon 2020 project I AM RRI-Webs of Innovation Value Chains (IVCs) of Additive Manufacturing (AM) formulated different types of agents, their characteristics and the strategies they follow.

financial investors, and consumers as well as commercial banks, the government and the central bank. To examine the impact of digital technologies on the economic system, they also include a new economic agent that develops intangible digital goods. He and Lee (2020) propose an ABM to investigate the impact of social culture on innovation diffusion. The model assumes that social culture has a direct effect on the structure of the small-world network and individual characteristics. Beckenbach, Briegel, and Daskalakis (2007) use an agent-based simulation of regional innovation dynamics that incorporates both explicit and implicit (shareable/non-shareable) knowledge sources. In the simulation, agents represent firms that can act in different ways, including routine operation, imitation, and innovation (individual as well as collaborative). They emphasize how these agents interact with regional innovation networks and integrate behavioral theories from cognitive psychology and organizational behavior.

Wang et al. (2014) adopt an ABM to simulate the processes of technological innovation and diffusion among firms in Chinese regions. The model creates precise scenarios that show the interaction of individual firms acting as agents in their geographical and economic environment. The intention of these interactions is to reflect patterns of behavior such as innovation, imitation and adoption of new technologies that are shaped by different economic policies and market conditions. Paier et al. (2017) use an ABM to analyze the effects of various public R&D policies on knowledge creation in the Austrian biotechnology sector. Their focus is on the development of a region's technological profile. They use patent data as knowledge representations and apply a detailed empirical initialization and calibration strategy with firm-level data to replicate the real dynamics and interactions between firms within the industry and validate the model. Furthermore, they incorporate qualitative data (expert knowledge) when conceptualizing the model and developing scenarios. Neuländtner (2020) propose an empirically grounded ABM to approximate the complex nature of the multiregional knowledge creation process for European regions. In particular, they focus on intra-regional characteristics and a specific embedding in the system of intra-regional and extra-regional R&D cooperation relations. They also provide first exemplary applications to demonstrate the potential of the model in terms of its robustness and empirical accuracy.

Zhong and He (2021) use ABM within an input-output (IO) analysis framework to examine the impact of the diffusion of technological innovations at the micro level on the dynamic changes in regional economic structures in large global economies (i.e. China, Japan, the United States, Russia, India and the European Union) at the macro level from 2007 to 2030. The model includes a large number of agents (heterogeneous firms) and simulates different policy scenarios. Zhong, Chen, and He (2022) utilize the same approach to investigate the diffusion of technological innovations and their impact on industrial structural change and the transfer of carbon emissions via trade in major global economies (i.e. China, Japan, the United States, Russia, India and the European Union) from 2007 to 2030. Varga-Csajkás, Sebestyén, and Varga (2023) use an ABM to analyze how start-up support can foster the emergence of new links in the innovation network of high-growth firms (gazelles) in Hungary. In order to find cooperation partners, the agents move towards each other in a two-dimensional abstract social space. They follow the principle of gravity.⁷ A regression analysis determines these parameters. The model's empirical foundation was provided by survey data (from 2014-2016) on the egocentric network of Hungarian gazelles, which includes information about innovation-purpose cooperation. Amendola et al. (2024) built an ABM to study the effects of different energy efficiency policies on energy efficiency, energy intensity, and macroeconomic dynamics. The model includes different agents, specifically capital-good firms, consumption-good firms, workers, banks, the government and the central bank. Policies range from direct technological policies, where a public research laboratory invests in R&D to establish a new technological energy efficiency paradigm, to taxes, incentives, and subsidies.

⁷ The mass and distance of the agents determine the force of attraction.

Table 1: A Synthesis of the Empirical Work: Agent-based modelling of regional innovation systems

	Parametrization	Calibration	Validation
Amendola et al. (2024)	Based on the literature	Indirect calibration approach	Replication of empirical stylized facts
Beckenbach, Briegel, and Daskalakis (2007)	Survey data	Empirical findings and survey data	Sensitivity analysis
Bertani et al. (2021)	Based on the literature	The model has not been calibrated to any specific real-world economy	Replication of empirical stylized facts
Cozzoni et al. (2021)	Based on the literature	Statistical techniques	Using existing theory or studies, Modeler experience and intuition, Conversations with subject-matter experts during development/face validity and observing the macro-level effects
He and Lee (2020)	Based on the literature	Statistical techniques	Empirical data
Neuländtner (2020)	Empirical data and user input	Empirical data and statistical techniques (Latin hypercube sampling)	Replication of empirical stylized facts and based on the empirical findings in related studies and Poisson regression model
Paier et al. (2017)	Empirical data	Based on expert knowledge and empirical data	Empirical data
Varga-Csajkás, Sebestyén, and Varga (2023)	Statistical techniques (Regression analysis)	Survey data and statistical techniques (Minimal distance approach)	Survey data
Wang et al. (2014)	Empirical data	Empirical data	Empirical data
Zhong and He (2021)	Choice of modeler	Empirical data	Empirical data and statistical techniques (regression statistics methods including correlation analysis, double-sample mean analysis, and Z-test)
Zhong, Chen, and He (2022)	Based on the Literature	Empirical data	Empirical data and statistical techniques (regression statistics methods, including correlation analysis, double-sample mean analysis, and Z-test)

4.2. Results

As the model assumptions are very diverse and shed light on different aspects of RIS, it is not feasible to compare the results in a systematic way. However, it is possible to gain valuable insights into the dynamics of RIS and the different ABM. Bertani et al. (2021) find that unemployment increases because the new jobs created in the digital sector, triggered by higher productivity of digital assets, do not compensate for job losses in mass production. Their results also show the emergence of the relevant stylized facts observed in the business domain, such as increasing returns, winner-take-most phenomena, and market lock-in. Cozzoni et al. (2021) argue that greater emphasis on RRI values in partner selection leads to increased heterogeneity within networks. According to He and Lee (2020), power distance and uncertainty avoidance (from Hofstede's cultural dimension theory) have a negative effect on innovation diffusion, while individualism has a positive effect on diffusion speed in the early phase. After the early phase of diffusion, the effect of uncertainty avoidance on diffusion speed becomes positive, and the negative effect of power distance becomes positive in the late stage. When uncertainty avoidance is high, innovation diffusion is influenced by the characteristics of the innovation. However, the influence of an innovation's characteristics on diffusion is limited when both individualism and uncertainty avoidance are low. They find a number of similarities in the diffusion patterns between the proposed ABM and actual diffusion data.

From a firm perspective, Beckenbach, Briegel, and Daskalakis (2007) indicate that experimental firms (radical innovators) tend to have a higher level of risk acceptance and are more likely to cooperate than firms which are cautious (Imitators). Wang et al. (2014) report that few firms conduct independent product innovation, with most preferring imitation and/or acquisitions. They also emphasize the role of preferential policies in promoting innovation diffusion in less developed areas, especially in central China, improving the attractiveness of the labor force in central, western, and northeastern China and reducing migration to the east. Varga-Csajkás, Sebestyén, and Varga (2023) identify negative impacts of geographical, social, and technological distance on innovation cooperation in Hungarian high-growth firms.

Neuländtner (2020) replicates empirical observations of spatial distribution of knowledge creation, highlighting regions like Île-de-France, Madrid, Catalunya as key hubs. Although they find no significant correlation between degree of technological specialization and knowledge output, specialized regions with industrial districts or sector-specific spillover effects and generalist regions that benefit from sectoral diversification are among the leading regions when it comes to knowledge creation. Paier et al. (2017) show that, in the context of the ex-ante impact assessment of public research policy in an industry-specific and national context, an empirically calibrated and transparent model design increases the credibility and robustness of the ABM approach.

Zhong and He (2021) show that process innovation promotes resource transfer between regions, while product innovation aids industrial structure upgrading in the U.S., suggesting differentiated innovation policies for global economic governance. In a complementary vein, Zhong, Chen, and He (2022) highlight the sectoral and regional differences in the impacts of technological innovation on industrial structural adjustment and emissions, noting that product innovation is more conducive in reducing trade impacts on the emissions of regional economies compared to process innovation. Amendola et al. (2024) conclude that in terms of energy efficiency, most policy measures (direct technological policies, where a public research laboratory invests in R&D to establish a new technological energy efficiency paradigm, taxes, incentives, and subsidies) effectively reduce energy intensity. However, the research laboratory has the highest effectiveness in increasing energy efficiency without a negative impact on macroeconomic conditions and public finances. They point out that most policies do not significantly induce macroeconomic rebound effects, suggesting that concerns in that regard

may be overstated. However, they also emphasize that a long-term commitment is needed to make this policy successful.

4.3. Methodological challenges and limitations

By now, ABM are mainly carried out on an abstract, theoretical level, lacking empirical foundation and hence, real-world applicability (Gilbert, Pyka, and Ahrweiler 2001; Crooks, Castle, and Batty 2008; Batty 2012; Ausloos, Dawid, and Merlone 2015; Vermeulen and Pyka 2018; Kamath, Sun, and Hermans 2022) or are only partially empirically based (He and Lee 2020; Bertani et al. 2021; Cozzoni et al. 2021). Reasons for that are data availability (Cozzoni et al. 2021) and the problematic relationship between ABM and empirical data (Varga-Csajkás, Sebestyén, and Varga 2023), especially when it comes to model validation (Windrum, Fagiolo, and Moneta 2007). For instance, Cozzoni et al. (2021) noted that while some data on Additive Manufacturing in the European market exist, they have not been sufficiently processed for complex validation processes. Similarly, Varga-Csajkás, Sebestyén, and Varga (2023) highlighted the limitations of using cross-sectional data and the necessity for representative samples and panel data to achieve generalizable results and relevant policy simulations. Moreover, it is justified that ABM are mainly used as conceptual tools, as they are generally considered as ideal learning tools for researchers who want to understand a system under different conditions by simulating the agents' interactions. The simplicity of agent rules is therefore usually an important aspect in the development of ABM (Zhang and Vorobeychik 2019). However, the ABM methodology has also been criticized for this simplicity, being considered as "toy models" that do not reflect reality (Garcia and Jager 2011). It is increasingly pointed out that the predictive power of the model is crucial when applying ABM to support policy decisions and that models that are mainly conceptual are not suitable for such tasks (Zhang and Vorobeychik 2019). However, there is also a trade-off between effort and outcome. Schinko et al. (2017) stresses that the inherent randomness in stochastic simulations, while closer to natural processes, increases model complexity significantly, requiring comprehensive simulation and analysis methods.

ABM research is also often criticized in the literature because it lacks a recognized methodological standard. Modeling issues have always required validation (Conway, Johnson, and Maxwell 1959), particularly when it comes to computational models (Carley 1996; Garcia, Rummel, and Hauser 2007). Validation is the process of evaluating how well the implemented model reflects reality. Unfortunately, there isn't a single, widely recognized method for validation, which may be the primary issue that prevents mainstream social scientists from accepting it in leading journals (Zhang and Vorobeychik 2019). Richiardi et al. (2006) emphasize in their protocol four potential methodological difficulties: linking to the literature, model structure, analysis, and replicability. In the course of our careful review, we find that most of these problems have been addressed or substantially reduced. Almost all of the papers reviewed include theoretical background and related work, sufficient description of model structure and a formal presentation. However, concerns about systematic quantitative calibration and validation using empirical data still remain. We note that the analyzed papers have different PCV strategies (see Table 1). Some papers use a literature base for parameterization (He and Lee 2020; Bertani et al. 2021; Cozzoni et al. 2021; Zhong, Chen, and He 2022; Amendola et al. 2024), empirical data (Wang et al. 2014; Paier et al. 2017; Neuländtner 2020) or statistical techniques (Varga-Csajkás, Sebestyén, and Varga 2023). In the case of calibration, many studies rely on empirical data (Beckenbach, Briegel, and Daskalakis 2007; Wang et al. 2014; Paier et al. 2017; Neuländtner 2020; Zhong and He 2021; Zhong, Chen, and He 2022), the choice of the modeler (Zhong and He 2021), statistical techniques (He and Lee 2020; Neuländtner 2020; Cozzoni et al. 2021; Varga-Csajkás, Sebestyén, and Varga 2023), combine empirical data with expert knowledge (Paier et al. 2017), use an indirect calibration

approach (Amendola et al. 2024) or do not calibrate to any specific real-world economy at all (Bertani et al. 2021). Validation is often carried out by replicating empirical data and/or stylized facts (Wang et al. 2014; Paier et al. 2017; He and Lee 2020; Neuländtner 2020; Bertani et al. 2021; Zhong and He 2021; Zhong, Chen, and He 2022; Amendola et al. 2024), statistical techniques (Zhong and He 2021; Zhong, Chen, and He 2022) or sensitivity analysis (Beckenbach, Briegel, and Daskalakis 2007).

5. Participatory modelling: Combining Foresight elements with ABM for innovation policy

In addition to the increasing interest in ABM for regional innovation (see Table 1), we can observe an upcoming debate on the notion of participatory modelling as an additional valuable element in the design, specification and interpretation of such models. However, elements of participatory modelling in ABM on regional innovation are yet scarce, although the literature increasingly emphasizes the usefulness of combining quantitative and qualitative methods – such as participatory modelling (also often referred to as combining foresight with modelling) – to analyze systems in more detail (Shaaban et al. 2023). In essence, moreover to quantitative scenarios, which are necessary to make accurate predictions about probabilities and possible outcomes, qualitative scenarios derived from participatory or foresight exercises provide useful further and often more comprehensive (e.g. societal) insights into possible futures (Shaaban et al. 2023).

In general, under participatory modelling we understand – broadly speaking – the integration of various stakeholders in the development, validation and implementation of quantitative models such as ABM (Ramanath and Gilbert 2004). In line with the bottom-up idea of ABM, it is possible to assign stakeholders a role in the model if they can be involved in the modeling process so that they can take action instead of an artificial agent (Axtell and Farmer 2022). Stakeholder involvement is also intended to increase the willingness to implement political measures based on the results (Voinov and Bousquet 2010; Zellner et al. 2012). Against this view, Durlauf (2012) argues that the complexity-approach in economics in general and the ABM methodology in particular “have no fundamental impact on policy evaluation” (Durlauf 2012, 68). To capture the complexity of innovation in RIS and to be better prepared for future trends, possible shocks due to environmental, market or societal developments, we need a commitment to evidence-based policies and a better understanding of the drivers of innovation. Participatory foresight—a structured discussion about the future among the key stakeholders—is particularly promising in this regard. It acknowledges the uncertainty of the future and encourages reflection on various potential future paths. There are different examples of participatory foresight e.g. scenario building, Delphi surveys, visioning and road mapping (Shaaban et al. 2023). These methods generate collective insights from the diversity of stakeholders' perspectives while simultaneously fostering a more robust extrapolation of current trends and a long-term, creative way of thinking beyond well-known pathways.

However, as mentioned above there are still only a limited number of studies that analyze RIS and include elements of participatory foresight in their empirical ABM, although it has the potential to advance the scientific debate in the field of innovation geography (Paier et al. 2017; Cozzoni et al. 2021). Paier et al. (2017) include expert knowledge during the conceptualization of the model and scenario formation. Cozzoni et al. (2021) have, among other things, conducted interviews with experts during the development of their model and used them to approach the validation process.

Still, outside the field of regional innovation there are several examples, especially in the field of environmental economics, that use participatory modeling in combination with ABM and demonstrate the value of stakeholder involvement at different stages (Zellner et al. 2012; Shaaban et al. 2023). Shaaban et al. (2023) first quantified the parameters in an internal online

focus group discussion by estimating how much the value of the indicators of these parameters could change by 2035 compared to their status quo in 2021 (for a detailed description see Shaaban et al. (2023, 7)). Furthermore, they conducted a two-hour workshop with experts to validate the parameters and create a sound basis for further modeling and scenario analysis. 12 scientists from different fields were invited, including agronomy, agricultural economics, environmental science, information technology, agricultural law and natural science, to reduce the number of parameters that were not relevant for the scenario assumptions. The parameters were divided into three groups and assigned to the experts according to their expertise. The assessment was carried out using five-level qualitative estimates (from “very low” to “very high”), which were applied to the scenarios. These qualitative evaluations are then converted into quantitative values to enable comparability. As there was disagreement on the estimated values and not enough time to discuss them in detail, they use the average of the quantified scores and round to the nearest quantitative value. Finally, they averaged the results of the two exercises (internal focus group and expert workshop) to determine the final values for the parameters.

Zellner et al. (2012) have organized expert workshops to promote a deep understanding of complex systems through participatory ABM. Stakeholder involvement is also intended to increase the willingness to implement policies based on the results of ABM. 16 stakeholders (homeowners, public officials, environmental organizations, and resource management professionals) who had played a role in the development of the McHenry County Water Resources Action Plan were invited. The workshops were conducted over four sessions over a three-month period. Each session was designed around a specific learning phase, ranging from an introduction to modeling to the application of detailed models. The sessions alternated between modeling activities and discussions, with participants being gradually introduced to models of increasing complexity. Participants worked in small groups of two to three people per computer, which allowed for direct interaction with the models. After the modeling work, group meetings were held to discuss the findings and develop planning proposals. Researchers guided participants through the exploration of the models and helped to adapt the models based on participant feedback. This included using NetLogo and adapting models. Participants provided feedback on agents, rules and parameters, which contributed to further model development. Discussions helped to clarify the complexity of the problems and to develop alternative policy approaches. In the later sessions, detailed simulation results were presented and explored by the participants. These results were used to evaluate potential policy scenarios and discuss future implementation strategies. However, they also highlight that one of the challenges was that some participants had difficulty using the computers and modeling tools, which led to a drop in participation. This required constant adaptation of the methodology by the researchers to encourage participation and understanding.

6. Conclusion

In this paper we highlight the transition from traditional linear models of innovation to more complex, systems-oriented perspectives that consider the heterogeneity of actors and the non-linearity of their interactions within regional contexts. Against this background, ABM is particularly suitable, offering a bottom-up approach that can simulate real-world scenarios and provide deeper insights into the emergent properties of RIS.

In the scope of our literature review, we identified eleven papers that are empirical, analyze RIS and use ABM (for a comprehensive overview see Table 1). These papers differ not only in their parametrization, calibration and validation strategy (e.g. some models use empirical parameterization, while others are theoretical), but also include various types of agents (firms, households, government entities, and research institutions), use different methods and address different questions.

Many papers do not fulfill one of the three criteria —being empirical, analyzing RIS, and utilizing ABM. Some employ ABM but focus solely on firm-level innovation, while others incorporate both ABM and RIS but remain largely theoretical, offering limited empirical validation. While theoretical ABM are valuable for conceptual explorations, there is a need for more empirical models that can offer practical, real-world applications, especially when formulating policy implications. Models that are mainly conceptual are poorly suited to derive such measures, as the predictive power of ABM is crucial. With advances in computing power and the availability of individualized data there are and will be more possibilities using ABM to model innovation systems.

Finally, incorporating foresight elements e.g., stakeholder involvement can enrich ABM and align them more closely with the needs and realities of regional innovation ecosystems. Participatory foresight emerges as a critical tool for enhancing the applicability and acceptance of ABM-based insights in policymaking. However, the literature indicates that participatory approaches remain underutilized within the context of RIS and empirical ABM. Even studies that incorporate such methods, such as those by Cozzoni et al. (2021) and Paier et al. (2017), raise doubts about whether they truly qualify as participatory modeling or foresight. Future research should focus on empirically grounded models that integrate foresight elements. This not only advance academic understanding but also informs effective policy interventions aimed at fostering RIS.

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